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A REVIEW OF POSSIBLE ENERGY FUEL FROM SOLID MUNICIPAL WASTE

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ABSTRACT

Rapid industrialization and population explosion in various parts of the especially developing country like India has led to the migration of people from villages to cities, which generate thousands tons of municipal solid waste daily, which is one of the important contributors for environmental degradation at national level. Municipal solid waste causes various hazards to inhabitants due to improper management. The energy crisis and environmental degradation are currently two important issues for global sustainable development. The proper management of municipal solid waste requires infrastructure, maintenance and upgrade for all activities. The municipal solid waste management system comprises with generation, storage, collection, transfer and transport, processing and disposal of solid wastes. In the present work, a comprehensive study has been made to provide a review of MSW management to evaluate the current status of waste to energy facilities for sustainable management, which will be helpful in tackling the huge quantity of waste and the problem of energy crisis and also evaluated with its advantages and disadvantages.

KEYWORDS: Energy generation, Municipal solid waste (MSW), Indian scenario